

THE MAIN FACTORS AFFECTING HEALTH NEGATIVELY

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Annotation: This article covers information about the basic factors that negatively affect human health. Moreover, recent researches and studies according to the theme were analyzed.

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It's no surprise that the way you live can have effects on your health. Generally speaking, a more healthy lifestyle leads to a more healthy life. Unfortunately, this goal is not often the easiest to achieve. So, let's break it down: here's how your health can be affected by your lifestyle choices.

- An Unhealthy Lifestyle

It may seem obvious, but if you use drugs, eat poorly, and refuse to exercise, these actions will negatively reflect on your health. They also can lead to outcomes where you end up hurt or unwell. For instance, 15,000 car injury deaths happen each year because of alcohol or other illicit drugs. Somebody who uses drugs and has little regard for your safety or the safety of others while under the influence will result in a negative effect on your health, along with detrimental consequences for those around you[1]. Keep in mind that drinking and driving is illegal and can result in big mistakes that you cannot take back. Eating poorly can have negative effects in almost any circumstance in your life. Most notably, it raises blood pressure and cholesterol levels. Once your body has increased difficulty pumping blood throughout its system, any future disease or infection will be that much harder to fight. For example, one in nine men will be diagnosed with prostate cancer in their lifetime, and an obese man may, therefore, have a more advanced disease. This can make it harder to treat. This is similar for heart problems. Having higher cholesterol and blood pressure makes it that much harder for your heart to pump blood throughout your body. Clogging your arteries is a big risk associated with being overweight. To avoid making matters worse or even getting there in the first place, eating right and exercising are important to making sure your health is in the best shape it can be.

- A Healthy Lifestyle

As mentioned, it's important to make sure you're eating right and getting some exercise. However, these are only the first steps you can take. There are plenty of other healthy choices you can make to lead a more health-centric lifestyle.

For starters, making sure you're following up with your doctor's appointments is a good decision. This will help ensure that you're taking care of all aspects of physical health, like your oral, visual, and ear health. You should also work on prioritizing your mental health since all these aspects of wellness tie into each other. For example, those with poor vision should avoid straining your eyes by investing in glasses or contact lenses. If you also drive, this is especially important for your health and the wellbeing of other drivers on the road.

Your oral health routine can have an impact on your chances of developing different gum cancers. Making sure you're getting your regular cleanings is important and making sure they look their best will impact your mental health, as well. According to the American Association of Orthodontists, approximately four million Americans wear braces. After all, it's important to feel good about how you look[2]. A healthy lifestyle is a life where your health and safety comes first. It's common for your unhealthy decisions to inadvertently affect others, as well. A healthy lifestyle demands that you're being intentional about the things you eat, who you interact with, how frequently you see your doctor, and how you feel about yourself. All of these things can either positively or negatively impact your life depending on how you adapt them into your lifestyle. An individual's social environment can negatively affect a person's health leading to obesity, mental health problems, and a higher risk of diseases. Typically, those that are lower on the social ladder are twice as likely to develop a health condition. A poor social environment can make a person feel anxious and stressed, which in the long-term can lead to physical medical conditions. Social environment factors are not the only aspects of one's life to consider when determining the risk for health conditions. However, the social environment is often overlooked. A social environment has to do with the culture and relationships that surround an individual. These factors include the type of neighborhood one lives in, how much money a person makes, the education one has, or the access a person has to specific resources.

Mental health problems have been the topic of many discussions recently. I believe that social environment factors affect mental health more than we know. One reasoning behind this is the social network of an individual[3]. There are two issues to consider here. The first being, if a person is diagnosed with depression, then they will tend to stray away from social interactions. They may avoid spending quality time with family and friends, which can lead to a deeper

depressed state. On the other hand, an individual may be diagnosed with a taboo illness. This may include diseases such as HIV or even diabetes. Depending on the age group and the type of relationships an individual has, this may lead to changes in one's social network. The change in social networks can result in a loss of friends, causing an individual to feel depressed in some ways.

Poverty is a problem across the globe, and there has yet to be a solution to the problem. One thing is for certain. Poor social environmental factors can have detrimental effects on health. Based on research and studies, it appears that poverty and health conditions go hand in hand. Unfortunately, many people have defined themselves around the type of job they have or how much money they make. For example, some may believe that the higher your salary, the higher your level of importance is. On top of this, those that tend to have higher salaries only surround themselves with people that have a similar income. The same is true for the person that has a lower income. We tend to surround ourselves with others that are on the same playing field as us. Therefore, our diversification is limited. This creates a culture that can be closed-minded and limits our social relationships to a certain type of people. Our limited diversification and closed-mindedness then bleed into other aspects of our social environment. Eventually, this can lead to the development of a whole community that has a low-income status.

Mental illness, substance abuse, unemployment, violence and poverty may have a negative impact on the well-being of individuals and carers. Drug and alcohol abuse may lead to physical and emotional neglect. Risk factors are the conditions that usually occur as the age of a person grows and largely affect a person's health. The risk factors which commonly arise from several effects on health are poor eating habits, poor sleep patterns, and lack of proper exercise. Health and age are the two important factors associated with the quantity of sleep[4]. If a person finds difficulty in maintaining sleep or the patterns of sleep that are causing uneasiness in the lifestyle then the condition is considered a disturbed Sleeping pattern.

To sum up, it may lead to the risk factors of anxiety, pain, or even depression. Lack of exercise is also considered a risk factor that is responsible for all cardiovascular diseases due to which many heart risk factors arise. According to research, it has been observed having an increased risk of cardiovascular diseases leads a person to anxiety, high anger, and even to physical or emotional stress. Studies have shown that the factor of proper sleep can overcome some of the risk factors which greatly affect a person's health. People taking an appropriate amount of sleep can have healthy lives as compared to those people who sleep for just a few hours. It is observed that a person's cardiovascular system continuously remains under pressure

and the levels of pressure cannot be reduced till a person takes a balanced amount of sleep. Researchers have shown that sleeping well keeps a person's health better. The benefits of sleep are observed in a wide range which makes a huge difference in the quality of life. From the reports, it has been concluded that adults of age 80 and above would need to sleep more hours than those adults of ages 65 to 79. The study results that about 7 to 8 hours of sleep is required for adults for proper functioning and attaining a healthy life.

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